

National Open Access Monitor Project

Danish Open Access Indicator Meeting, 10th February 2023

Present:

- Danish Open Access Indicator: Hanne-Louise Kirkegaard; Karen Hytteballe Ibanez
- National Open Access Monitor Project Advisory Group: Fran Callaghan; Caleb Derven; Eoin Kenny; Kevin Kiely; Andrew Simpson.
- National Open Access Monitor Project Manager: Catherine Ferris

Agenda: Project plan action "Consult with the providers of the Danish and French national monitoring solutions and create a report which documents their advice, lessons learnt, and methods/tools that could be adapted or reused in the Irish context."

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Lessons learnt:

- Challenges with researcher inputted RIS metadata quality. This is improving, after much dialogue/handholding/help. Good quality CRIS data is critical to accurate measurement.
- Whitelist of OA repositories e.g. Arxiv, Pubmed Central, etc or ISSN matches DOAJ.
- Book Chapters originally planned to be within scope, but stakeholders concluded to remove from scope, now just Journal Articles and Conference Papers.
- System records embargo details, but they are not monitored
- CRIS data harvested through webservice. CRIS data will contain both manually registered and from third-party e.g. Scopus. Open data not a consideration for the Danish Open Access Indicator.
- No additional funding from Ministry required to enable monitoring – existing Pure CRIS infrastructure was in place, together with Danish national exchange format. Project funding was provided to assist institutions and small Danish journals to develop OA skills.
- Existing BFI processes in place, with dedicated resources, to encourage university researchers to populate CRIS systems – a good foundation for Indicator.
- Danish government pays for the running of the national open access monitor indicator.

Methods/tools that could be adapted or reused in the Irish context:

- Implement test runs for data gathering from institutions. Purpose: check harvesting is working correctly; institutions can review results in advance of monitoring.
- OA monitoring done on an annual basis with a two-year window of previous data (i.e. 2023 monitor on 2021 data).
- Sherpa ROME0 used to establish OA status of Journals, including embargo periods
- DOAJ to identify Gold OA
- Unpaywall hints to help institutions identify publications which may not have been registered yet; don't use it as a source (different OA definition; challenges with non-Crossref DOIs)

Advice:

- Annual soft-target % OA set by Ministry (rather than 100% in 2030) helps to motivate. E.g. 2018 target 36% <https://oaindikator.dk/en/overview/>
- Importance to enable partner dialogue with stakeholders. Enables updating service based on feedback. Research Office / Senior Uni buy in is helpful to support and impact the implementation of open access. Ensure stakeholders can feel ownership of the process and how they're represented.
- Important to have professional support function at universities to help researchers with open access practices.
- Key issue: keep all processes and data transparent.